

Effect of Isometric and Isotonic Exercise on Total Knee Arthroplasty Outcome

Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis

Farzad Ravari

Dubai Medical University Hospital

Background. Rehabilitation is commonly advised before and after total knee arthroplasty although its efficacy and effectiveness need more evaluation.

Purpose. There are some discrepancies in the literature regarding the effect of isotonic and isometric exercise before and after total knee arthroplasty (TKA) on the outcome of patients, some studies believe in the efficacy and effectiveness of exercise before and after and some believe only after surgery, therefore we conducted this systematic review and meta-analysis.

Data Source. Our systematic review concentrates on the effect of isometric and isotonic exercise on patients with TKA based on pain score and functional score and psycho-social function. In this study, the source of data is from the following databases: Embase, Medline, and CINAHL, the Cochrane Library.

Study Selection. Covidence tools were used for searching management and study selection.

Data Extraction and Synthesis. Data extraction was done by reviewing the articles and tabulating the data in excel sheath, and finally, data synthesis and analysis were done by RevMan.

Limitations. One of the limitations of the study was the quality of the evidence and heterogeneity in some studies due to baseline data missing.

Conclusion. This study evaluates the effect of isometric and isotonic exercise on the outcome of total knee arthroplasty. It also explains the role of these exercises in pain score, functional score, and psychosocial function if it is done before surgery, although it could improve self-confidence, adoption of surgery, and arthritis efficacy score, therefore prehabilitation with isometric and isotonic exercises will reduce the length of stay at the hospital (LOS) and improve daily activity in comparison to cases that did rehabilitation with isometric and isotonic exercises only after surgery. In this study, I found prehabilitation mainly improves TUG in the patient with TKA and does not significantly improve pain score, QOL, ADL, 6MW, or ROM, but post-operative

rehabilitation with isotonic and isometric exercise will improve 6MWT and QOL but does not significantly improve pain score in the patients undergoing TKA.

Keywords. Prehabilitation, Total knee arthroplasty, Isometric exercise, Isotonic exercise, osteoarthritis

Background

Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is defined as the degenerative change in joint cartilage and is one of the most common joint problems that cause pain, impairs function, and lead to disability in the elderly.[1] OA can be primary or secondary (post-traumatic or following inflammatory disease).[2] According to Cui et al (2003),[3] knee osteoarthritis is present in 2% of individuals 20 years and older and increases with age. In the United States, research shows that OA affects approximately 10% of males and 13% of females older than 60 years[3], and in Canada approximately 35% of the population experience OA after the age of 80 years old.[4] Approximately 10% of direct medical costs are related to knee OA-related care with an estimated cost of CAD15,000 to CAD20,000 per patient annually.[5]

Treatment of knee OA typically includes medication, rehabilitation, and modification of lifestyle behavior (e.g., physical activity). If no improvement is experienced by these conservative treatments, then surgery in the form of total knee arthroplasty (TKA) is commonly recommended.[6]

Isometric exercises are performed when individuals contract and hold their muscles without visible movement in the angle of the joints (e.g., plank, wall sit). These types of exercises are shown to improve strength and stability and maintain lower blood pressure during exercise.[7] Isotonic exercise on the other hand involves movement and bending of joints with constant weight or tension such as cycling and squats, these types of exercises also improve muscle strength and muscle building. The poor preoperative status such as weakness in lower

limb muscles will affect the postoperative outcome, so the training of lower limb muscles will improve the preoperative status and postoperative outcomes.[8]

The power of the quadriceps muscle will reduce to 60%, and activity decreased by 17 % following total knee arthroplasty[9].⁹ Therefore training of lower limb muscles before surgery (prehabilitation) could improve the capability to endure stress and postoperative outcomes, it is shown, it reduces the recovery period, improves self-confidence and function after surgery.

Although some studies do not support the effect of routine prehabilitation in the outcome of TKA.[10] Studies by Granicher (2020) and Brown (2012)[11], [12] suggest, there are some differences in the effectiveness of pre-operative and post-operative rehabilitation on the outcome of TKA, especially in knee range of motion (ROM) and quality of life (QOL).[13]

Castrodad et al. (2019) presented, the power of quadriceps muscle following TKA will be decreased, and it affects the outcome of surgery, therefore, the training of quadriceps before surgery may improve postoperative pain and decrease the length of stay (LOS) in hospital.[14], [15]

Due to different ideas about the efficacy and effectiveness of these exercises, more work needs to be done to develop a greater understanding of the effects of prehabilitation, given existing discrepancies in literature.

Due to the argument, it requires conducting a systematic review in literature for clarification of the effect of pre-operative or post-operative rehabilitation on the outcome of TKA.

Purposes

Due to discrepancy in the effect of rehabilitation before and after TKA on the outcome of surgery, in this study as a systematic review and meta-analysis, we planned to evaluate the effect

of isometric and isotonic exercises on the outcome of TKA such as pain, movement, and psychosocial function if it performed before and/ or after surgery.

Methods

The reporting in this review follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses guidelines (PRISMA) to improve the reporting of systematic reviews and meta-analyses. The study is registered in the Open Science Framework (OSF) with registration number: <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/Q527H>

Data Sources and Searches

We searched MEDLINE (Ovid, PubMed), EMBASE, and CINAHL. We searched the papers that were published from 2010, because new versions of TKA, (cruciate-retaining (CR), high-flex TKAs) and techniques were developed primarily after this period.¹⁷ Thus, we deemed that evidence published before 2010 would not be comparable to those published after 2010. Our search strategy included the keywords of knee osteoarthritis, rehabilitation pre-operative and/or post-operative, total knee arthroplasty (appendix).

Study Selection

Type of Study. We included a randomized control trial (RCTs) comparing a control group that received only usual care with an intervention group that received isometric and isotonic exercise before and/ or after TKA.

Inclusion/ Exclusion Criteria. Based on the PICO model (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome) is as follows:

Participants. All patients 19 years old and older who are scheduled for TKA for any reason are included in this study.

Intervention. The intervention group has received isometric and isotonic exercise before and/ or after surgery.

Comparison. The Control group only had usual care before and/or after surgery.

Outcome. Studies we included if they reported on the following variables: Pain (e.g. visual analog scale (VAS) for documentation of acute or chronic pain and is defined from 0 scores indicates no pain to 10 for extreme pain); functional outcomes using Knee injury and Osteoarthritis Outcome Score (KOOS Score) is the patient self-reported assessment to evaluate short and long term follow up of knee injury, it includes 42 items in 5 groups; pain, symptoms, activities of daily living (ADL) such as walking up and down the stairs, walking, shopping; sport and recreational activities such as Time up to go (TUG) and Six minutes walking time (6MWT), jumping, running, bending or Range of movement (ROM). Quality of life (QOL) based on the modification of lifestyle and psychosocial outcomes (e.g., self-confidence due to impaction of knee problem).[16]

Studies using electrical modalities such as Trans-electro-cutaneous nerve stimulation (TENS) for stimulation of muscle and continuous passive movement (CPM) machines were excluded from the review because these modalities are not included in active exercises. Studies with a PEDro scale of less than 6 and “low” and “very low” GRADE certainty of the evidence for outcome measurements were excluded from the study because of the low quality of evidence.

Data Extraction and Quality Assessment

Data from eligible studies were tabulated using a study-specific data extraction template. Extracted data included the year of study, country, sample size, sample characteristics, detail of the experimental and control interventions, outcome, and results. We contacted the corresponding authors of the studies for additional details for missing data.

All searched for studies (titles and abstracts) from databases were exported to a reference management software tool (Covidence) to identify and track all relevant studies based on eligibility criteria. The lead reviewer conducted a full-text review of papers to determine final

eligibility. Reasons for excluding papers were recorded in the PRISMA flow chart (Fig. 1). Any discrepancies between the reviewers about study selection were resolved by discussion with the other reviewers and authors.

Unclear and missing data were resolved by contacting the corresponding authors for more information. Two reviewers evaluated the methodological quality of included studies, such as randomization, blinding, and intention to treat using the 11-item PEDro scale[17] scoring from 0-10 and scores, less than 6 indicated low methodological quality and were excluded from our study (Table 2).

GRADE (Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development, and Evaluation)[18], [19] is a framework for the reliability of studies and quality of evidence-based on the risk of bias, imprecision, inconsistency, indirectness, and publication bias for rating down, and could be rated up for large magnitude of effect, dose-response gradient, and the presence of any residual confounding effects that would decrease the magnitude of effect.[17] Finally recommendation according to the degree of confidence and rating as "high", "moderate", "low" or "very low". A high rating indicates the true effect is similar to the estimated effect, a moderate rating indicates that the true effect is probably close to the estimated effect, a low rating indicates that the true effect might be different from the estimated effect and a very low rating indicates that true effect probably is different from the estimated effect.[17]

In this study quality assessment was done with GRADEpro GDT application, all measurement outcomes separately were evaluated for the type of study design, risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision, number of participants, confidence interval 95%, and overall certainty of evidence classified into four groups “high”, “moderate”, “low” and “very low” (Table 4, 5).

Meta-Analysis

All randomized controlled trials with baseline and final data were included in our meta-analysis for evaluation of isometric and isotonic exercises: 1) Pre-operative; 2) post-operative; 3) Pre and Post-operative. The standardized mean difference (SMD) was used for continuous data along with 95% confidence intervals (CI) (SMD is calculated by the difference of intervention improvement and control improvement divided by pooled standard deviation).[18]

Forest plots were used to graphically depict the meta-analyses. Statistical significance was set at 0.05 in RevMan software to determine the weight, confidence intervals, p-value, I^2 , and forest plot as well.[20] For $I^2 \leq 50\%$ which indicates little statistical heterogeneity, we used a fixed-effect model, and for $I^2 > 50\%$ as high heterogeneity, a random effect model was used for meta-analysis.[18] A meta-analysis was performed on all outcomes that have pre-post or change data from at least 2 RCTs that demonstrate sufficient homogeneity across studies.

In studies with multiple time points, the mean difference between baseline and final data calculated for analysis and standard deviation (SD) was considered as baseline data SD. Heterogeneity indicates variability in data in different studies and is classified as 1) Clinical: Differences in participants, interventions, or outcomes, 2) Methodological: Differences in study design, risk of bias, 3) Statistical: Variation in intervention effects or results.[21] Therefore similarity and dissimilarity of studies determine the clinical and methodological heterogeneity and clinical and methodological heterogeneity were determined subjectively by the reviewers (Fig. 2-13).

We used I^2 as an indicator of statistical heterogeneity. An $I^2 \leq 50\%$ indicated little heterogeneity and more in favor of homogeneity therefore a fixed effect model was used for meta-analysis. If $I^2 > 50\%$ this indicated high heterogeneity, and thus we used a random effect model for analysis.[20]

Sensitivity Analysis is a method to determine if meta-analysis results are affected by changes in methods, models, and values of unmeasured variables.[15] We performed sensitivity analyses by excluding studies of low quality as determined by a PEDro score of 6 or less.

Results

In this study, 1082 studies were selected based on eligibility with inclusion/exclusion criteria, 245 studies were excluded due to duplicate studies and out of 837 remaining studies, 750 studies for irrelevant titles were removed. Full-text articles were reviewed in 87 studies and that 58 studies out of 87 were excluded due to wrong intervention, outcome, indication, and people population, and finally, 29 studies were selected for final systematic review and meta-analysis.

All included studies for review were described with study design, quality, participants, intervention, comparator, and outcomes. Randomized controlled trials with pre-post data on an outcome of interest were included in our meta-analysis for evaluating the effect of isometric and isotonic exercises: 1) Pre-operative; 2) postoperative; 3) Pre- and Post-operative.

Quality of study was evaluated with PEDro scale and all studies with a score less than 6 as low methodological quality studies were excluded from the analysis.

Quality of outcomes was evaluated by GRADEpro GDT application and all outcomes in rehabilitation, post-operative and control groups were measured. Based on evaluation in GRADEpro GDT application; the outcome measurements with “high” and “moderate” certainty of evidence are included in the study for analysis, “low” and “very low” certainty of the evidence was excluded (Table.2).

Discussion

The rationale of this study as a systematic review and meta-analysis was evaluation the effect of isometric and isotonic exercise on the outcome of total knee arthroplasty in three groups of pre-operative and/or post-operative. Due to controversy in the literature about the effect of

rehabilitation before and/or after surgery and based on our knowledge that rehabilitation requires spending time and money, therefore, determination the effectiveness and efficacy of rehabilitation pre-operative and/or post-operative on the outcome of TKA plays a significant role in the utilization of resources to get better results.

The quality of studies and outcome measurements were evaluated by PEDro and GRADE in this study and we tried to reduce bias as much as possible. Based on GRADE all outcome measurements were evaluated for the certainty of evidence; the “high” certainty of evidence outcome measurements included TUG, ADL, QOL, VAS, ROM, and the “moderate” certainty of evidence included 6MWT and Sports activities. Detail of evaluation based on GRADE summarized in tables 4 and 5.

Analysis of data revealed that there is no significant difference in pain score in the prehabilitation group compared to the control group. Time up to go (TUG) showed significant improvement in patients with prehabilitation. Analysis of data and forest plots also demonstrated there is no significant improvement in sport and activities in the pre-operative group in comparison to the control group. The range of movement of the knee did not confirm major improvement in the prehabilitation group in comparison to the control group. In addition, evaluation of 6 minutes walking time (6MWT) and Activity of daily living (ADL) did not prove an improvement following prehabilitation.

Statistical analysis of the Quality of Life (QOL) in the patient who received post-operative rehabilitation revealed slight improvement but there was no improvement in sport and activities in the prehabilitation group as well.

In this systematic review, several articles were evaluated and analyzed for outcomes measurement, although there was some limitation in this study regarding baseline and final data, finally following analysis of data it was showed prehabilitation mainly improves TUG in the

patient with TKA and did not significantly improve pain score, QOL, ADL, 6MWT or ROM, and post-operative rehabilitation improves 6mW and QOL but not significantly improve pain score in the patients those undergoing TKA.

Based on the findings of this systematic review and meta-analysis, the efficacy and effectiveness of Prehabilitation are not significantly higher than rehabilitation after surgery, therefore instead of spending time and resources for prehabilitation, it is suggested to use rehabilitation after surgery to save money, time and reduce the exhaustion of patients and rehabilitation team as well.

Study Limitation

Quality of the evidence and heterogeneity of the studies due to baseline data missing in some studies were limitations of the study.

Further Research

Future studies are needed to clarify the efficacy and effectiveness of rehabilitation before and after TKA.

Acknowledgment

We would like to acknowledge Ms. Charlotte Beck, Librarian at the University of British Columbia, for her assistance in developing the search strategy.

Authors' contributions

FR conceptualization of study wrote the first draft of the manuscript; WCM conceptualization of the study, edited manuscript; BMS conceptualization of the study, edited manuscript

Funding

N/A

Availability of data and materials

N/A

Ethics approval and consent to participate

N/A

Consent for publication

N/A

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Abbreviations

TKA: Total Knee Arthroplasty, Risk Ratio: RRs, Odds ratio: ORs, Length of stay: LOS,

ROM: Range of Movement,

Systematic Review Registration

The study registered in Open Science Framework (OSF) with registration number:

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/Q527H>

References

- [1] E. O. Huber, R. A. de Bie, E. M. Roos, and H. A. Bischoff-Ferrari, "Effect of pre-operative neuromuscular training on functional outcome after total knee replacement: a randomized-controlled trial," *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 157, 2013, doi: 10.1186/1471-2474-14-157.
- [2] Hunter Hsu and Ryan M. Siwiec, "Knee osteoarthritis," www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK507884/, 2020.
- [3] Y. Zhang and J. M. Jordan, "Epidemiology of osteoarthritis," *Clinics in geriatric medicine*, vol. 26, no. 3, pp. 355–369, Aug. 2010, doi: 10.1016/j.cger.2010.03.001.
- [4] R. Birtwhistle *et al.*, "Prevalence and management of osteoarthritis in primary care: an epidemiologic cohort study from the Canadian Primary Care Sentinel Surveillance Network," *CMAJ open*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. E270–E275, Jul. 2015, doi: 10.9778/cmajo.20150018.
- [5] E. Losina *et al.*, "Lifetime medical costs of knee osteoarthritis management in the United States: impact of extending indications for total knee arthroplasty," *Arthritis care & research*, vol. 67, no. 2, pp. 203–215, Feb. 2015, doi: 10.1002/acr.22412.
- [6] E. Aytekin *et al.*, "The effect of a 12 week prehabilitation program on pain and function for patients undergoing total knee arthroplasty: A prospective controlled study," *Journal of clinical orthopaedics and trauma*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 345–349, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jcot.2018.04.006.
- [7] M.-H. Huang, Y.-S. Lin, R.-C. Yang, and C.-L. Lee, "A comparison of various therapeutic exercises on the functional status of patients with knee osteoarthritis," *Seminars in Arthritis and Rheumatism*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 398–406, 2003, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1053/sarh.2003.50021>.
- [8] B. , M. T. , M. I. , H. P. M. , S. K. , & D. U. Skoffer, "Efficacy of Preoperative Progressive Resistance Training on Postoperative Outcomes in Patients Undergoing Total Knee Arthroplasty. Arthritis care & research," *Arthritis care & research*, 2016.
- [9] D. Jahic, D. Omerovic, A. T. Tanovic, F. Dzankovic, and M. T. Campara, "The Effect of Prehabilitation on Postoperative Outcome in Patients Following Primary Total Knee Arthroplasty," *Medical archives (Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina)*, vol. 72, no. 6, pp. 439–443, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.5455/medarh.2018.72.439-443.
- [10] M. S. Mat Eil Ismail, M. A. Sharifudin, A. A. Shokri, and S. Ab Rahman, "Preoperative physiotherapy and short-term functional outcomes of primary total knee arthroplasty," *Singapore medical journal*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 138–143, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.11622/smedj.2016055.
- [11] K. Brown, J. A. Brosky, R. Topp, and A. S. Lajoie, "Prehabilitation and Quality of Life Three Months after Total Knee Arthroplasty: A Pilot Study," *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, vol. 115, no. 3, pp. 765–774, Dec. 2012, doi: 10.2466/15.06.10.PMS.115.6.765-774.
- [12] P. Gränicher, T. Stöggel, S. F. Fucentese, R. Adelsberger, and J. Swanenburg, "Preoperative exercise in patients undergoing total knee arthroplasty: a pilot randomized controlled trial," *Archives of Physiotherapy*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 13, 2020, doi: 10.1186/s40945-020-00085-9.

- [13] F. Matassi, J. Duerinckx, H. Vandenneucker, and J. Bellemans, "Range of motion after total knee arthroplasty: the effect of a preoperative home exercise program," *Knee Surgery, Sports Traumatology, Arthroscopy*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 703–709, 2014, doi: 10.1007/s00167-012-2349-z.
- [14] I. M. Dávila Castrodad *et al.*, "Rehabilitation protocols following total knee arthroplasty: a review of study designs and outcome measures," *Annals of translational medicine*, vol. 7, no. Suppl 7, pp. S255–S255, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.21037/atm.2019.08.15.
- [15] T. Bandholm, T. W. Wainwright, and H. Kehlet, "Rehabilitation strategies for optimisation of functional recovery after major joint replacement," *Journal of experimental orthopaedics*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 44, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.1186/s40634-018-0156-2.
- [16] E. M. Roos and L. S. Lohmander, "The Knee injury and Osteoarthritis Outcome Score (KOOS): from joint injury to osteoarthritis," *Health and quality of life outcomes*, vol. 1, p. 64, Nov. 2003, doi: 10.1186/1477-7525-1-64.
- [17] N. A. de Morton, "The PEDro scale is a valid measure of the methodological quality of clinical trials: a demographic study," *Australian Journal of Physiotherapy*, vol. 55, no. 2, pp. 129–133, 2009, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0004-9514\(09\)70043-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0004-9514(09)70043-1).
- [18] The Cochrane Collaboration, "GRADE in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions," <https://training.cochrane.org/online-learning/cochrane-methodology/grade-approach/grade-cochrane-handbook>, 2021.
- [19] British Medical Journal, "What is the GRADE," *British Medical Journal*, 2020.
- [20] A. Alghadir, Z. A. Iqbal, and S. Anwer, "Comparison of the effect of pre- and post-operative physical therapy versus post-operative physical therapy alone on pain and recovery of function after total knee arthroplasty," *Journal of physical therapy science*, vol. 28, no. 10, pp. 2754–2758, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1589/jpts.28.2754.
- [21] M. Siebert, "Heterogeneity: what is it and why does it matter? ," <https://s4be.cochrane.org/blog/2018/11/29/what-is-heterogeneity/>, 2018.
- [22] E. Coudeyre, C. Jardin, P. Givron, P. Ribinik, M. Revel, and F. Rannou, "Could preoperative rehabilitation modify postoperative outcomes after total hip and knee arthroplasty? Elaboration of French clinical practice guidelines," *Annales de réadaptation et de médecine physique : revue scientifique de la Société française de rééducation fonctionnelle de réadaptation et de médecine physique*, vol. 50, pp. 189–197, May 2007, doi: 10.1016/j.annrmp.2007.02.002.
- [23] J. Dennis, V. Wylde, R. Gooberman-Hill, A. W. Blom, and A. D. Beswick, "Effects of presurgical interventions on chronic pain after total knee replacement: a systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials," *BMJ Open*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. e033248, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2019-033248.
- [24] EduPristine, "All you want to know about Sensitivity Analysis," <https://www.edupristine.com/blog/all-about-sensitivity-analysis>, 2018.
- [25] E. R. Vina and C. K. Kwok, "Epidemiology of osteoarthritis: literature update," *Current opinion in rheumatology*, vol. 30, no. 2, pp. 160–167, Mar. 2018, doi: 10.1097/BOR.0000000000000479.
- [26] S. v Faraone, "Interpreting estimates of treatment effects: implications for managed care," *P & T: a peer-reviewed journal for formulary management*, vol. 33, no. 12, pp. 700–711, Dec. 2008, [Online]. Available: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19750051>

- [27] S. Goodman and K. Dickersin, "Metabias: A Challenge for Comparative Effectiveness Research," *Annals of Internal Medicine*, vol. 155, no. 1, pp. 61–62, Jul. 2011, doi: 10.7326/0003-4819-155-1-201107050-00010.
- [28] M. S. Ibrahim, S. Alazzawi, I. Nizam, and F. S. Haddad, "An evidence-based review of enhanced recovery interventions in knee replacement surgery," *Annals of the Royal College of Surgeons of England*, vol. 95, no. 6, pp. 386–389, Sep. 2013, doi: 10.1308/003588413X13629960046435.
- [29] C. A. Jacobs and C. P. Christensen, "Correlations between knee society function scores and functional force measures," *Clinical orthopaedics and related research*, vol. 467, no. 9, pp. 2414–2419, Sep. 2009, doi: 10.1007/s11999-009-0811-0.
- [30] S. , L. C. , N. V. , V. R. L. , & A. M. S. Lee, "Do isometric, isotonic and/or isokinetic strength trainings produce different strength outcomes?," *Journal of bodywork and movement therapies*, 22(2), pp. 430–437, 2017.
- [31] Y. Lin, S.-Y. Lee, W.-R. Su, C.-C. Kao, T.-W. Tai, and T.-B. Chen, "Effects of nurse-led lower extremity strength training on knee function recovery in patients who underwent total knee replacement," *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, vol. 27, p. 18361845, 2018.
- [32] C. Lisi *et al.*, "Early rehabilitation after elective total knee arthroplasty," *Acta bio-medica : Atenei Parmensis*, vol. 88, no. 4S, pp. 56–61, Oct. 2017, doi: 10.23750/abm.v88i4-S.5154.
- [33] I. F. H. Koblbauer *et al.*, "Reliability of maximal isometric knee strength testing with modified hand-held dynamometry in patients awaiting total knee arthroplasty: useful in research and individual patient settings? A reliability study," *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 249, 2011, doi: 10.1186/1471-2474-12-249.
- [34] Y. Kondo *et al.*, "Short-Term Effects of Isometric Quadriceps Muscle Exercise with Auditory and Visual Feedback on Pain, Physical Function, and Performance after Total Knee Arthroplasty: A Randomized Controlled Trial," *The Journal of Knee Surgery*, Nov. 2020, doi: 10.1055/s-0040-1721035.
- [35] N. S. Labraca, A. M. Castro-Sánchez, G. A. Matarán-Peñarrocha, M. Arroyo-Morales, M. del M. Sánchez-Joya, and C. Moreno-Lorenzo, "Benefits of starting rehabilitation within 24 hours of primary total knee arthroplasty: randomized clinical trial," *Clinical Rehabilitation*, vol. 25, no. 6, pp. 557–566, Mar. 2011, doi: 10.1177/0269215510393759.
- [36] J. Leppink, P. O'Sullivan, and K. Winston, "Effect size - large, medium, and small," *Perspectives on medical education*, vol. 5, no. 6, pp. 347–349, Dec. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s40037-016-0308-y.
- [37] S. Lewis and M. Clarke, "Forest plots: trying to see the wood and the trees," *BMJ*, vol. 322, no. 7300, p. 1479, Jun. 2001, doi: 10.1136/bmj.322.7300.1479.
- [38] A. L. C. Martimbianco, F. R. Calabrese, L. A. N. Iha, M. Petrilli, O. Lira Neto, and M. Carneiro Filho, "Reliability of the 'American Knee Society Score' (AKSS)," *Acta ortopedica brasileira*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 34–38, 2012, doi: 10.1590/S1413-78522012000100007.
- [39] R. M. Nunley *et al.*, "New total knee arthroplasty designs: do young patients notice?," *Clinical orthopaedics and related research*, vol. 473, no. 1, pp. 101–108, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1007/s11999-014-3713-8.
- [40] W. Peter *et al.*, "The provision of preoperative and postoperative physical therapy in elderly people with hip and knee osteoarthritis undergoing primary joint replacement

- surgery," *Current Orthopaedic Practice*, vol. 27, pp. 173–183, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1097/BCO.0000000000000347.
- [41] F. Pozzi, D. K. White, L. Snyder-Mackler, and J. A. Zeni, "Restoring physical function after knee replacement: a cross sectional comparison of progressive strengthening vs standard physical therapy," *Physiotherapy Theory and Practice*, vol. 36, no. 1, pp. 122–133, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1080/09593985.2018.1479475.
- [42] Y.-H. Pua *et al.*, "Comparative performance of isometric and isotonic quadriceps strength testing in total knee arthroplasty," *Musculoskeletal Science and Practice*, vol. 37, pp. 17–19, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.msksp.2018.06.008>.
- [43] P. Ranganathan, R. Aggarwal, and C. S. Pramesh, "Common pitfalls in statistical analysis: Odds versus risk," *Perspectives in clinical research*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 222–224, 2015, doi: 10.4103/2229-3485.167092.
- [44] R. Sharma, M. A. Ardebili, and I. N. Abdulla, "Does Rehabilitation before Total Knee Arthroplasty Benefit Postoperative Recovery? A Systematic Review," *Indian journal of orthopaedics*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 138–147, 2019, doi: 10.4103/ortho.IJOrtho_643_17.
- [45] L. Thabane *et al.*, "A tutorial on sensitivity analyses in clinical trials: the what, why, when and how," *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 92, 2013, doi: 10.1186/1471-2288-13-92.
- [46] A. Villadsen, S. Overgaard, A. Holsgaard-Larsen, R. Christensen, and E. M. Roos, "Postoperative effects of neuromuscular exercise prior to hip or knee arthroplasty: a randomised controlled trial," *Annals of the Rheumatic Diseases*, vol. 73, no. 6, p. 1130, Jun. 2014, doi: 10.1136/annrheumdis-2012-203135.
- [47] L. Wang, M. Lee, Z. Zhang, J. Moodie, D. Cheng, and J. Martin, "Does preoperative rehabilitation for patients planning to undergo joint replacement surgery improve outcomes? A systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials," *BMJ Open*, vol. 6, p. e009857, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2015-009857.
- [48] G. Rutherford, H. Horvath, G. Kennedy, and P. Volberding, *Quality of evidence supporting the World Health Organization's 2013 consolidated guidelines on the use of antiretroviral drugs for treating and preventing HIV infection (Abstract #THPE318)*. 2014.

Tables

Fig. 1- PRISMA Chart

Study	Eligibility Criteria	Random Allocation	Concealed Allocation	Baseline Comparability	Participant Blinded	Clinician Blinded	Assessor Blinded	ata for at Least 1 Outcome From >85% of Participants	No Missing Data or If Missing, Intention-to-Treat Analysis	Between-Groups Analysis	Point Estimates and Variability	Total Score (/10)
-------	----------------------	-------------------	----------------------	------------------------	---------------------	-------------------	------------------	--	--	-------------------------	---------------------------------	-------------------

Swank et.al	1	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	8
Alghadir et al.	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	7
MatEri Ismail et al	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Jahic et al	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Federico Pozzi et al	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	0	1	6
Skoffer et al	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Iskender et al.	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	7
Cavill et al.	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	7
Pua et al	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	7
Labraca et al.	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Kondo et al.	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Lin et al.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10
Aytekin et al.	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Tanaka.et al	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10
Calatayud et al.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10
Granicher et al.	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	10
Villadsen A. et al	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	8
Clode et al.	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
McKay et al	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	9
Brown et al.	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	8
Claudio et al.	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	5
Moe et al.	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	4
Huber et al	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	4
Brosky et al.	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	4

Table 2- PEDro Scale (24) (25) (26) (27) (28) (29) (30) (31) (32) (33) (34) (35) (36) (37) (38) (39) (40) (41) (42) (43) (44) (45) (46)
(47) (48) (49) (50) (51) (52) (53) (54) (55) (56) (57)

Author	Characteristics/ Control group	Characteristics/ Intrv. group	Intervention	Outcome
Swank et.al	N:35, Age: 62.6(7.6), Weight: 95.3(23.4), BMI: 32.9(5.7), Race: white 30, Minority 4, Gender: male 13, female 22	N:36, Age: 63.1(7.3), Weight: 98.9(19.9), BMI: 35.9(8.5), Race: white 28, Minority 7, Gender: male 12, female 24	usual care (UC)group (n= 36) or usual care and exercise (UC + EX) group (n=35); included resistance training using bands, flexibility, and step training at least 3 times per week for 4–8 weeks before their TKA in addition to UC	Functional outcome improved by prehabilitation, but it does not improve pain
Alghadir et al.	N=25, female=9, male 16, Age= 48-80, post-op rehabilitation	N=25, female=9, male 16, Age= 48-80, pre & post op rehabilitation	Strengthening and mobility exercises, proper techniques of transfers, and gait training with assistive devices (stick or walker)	No difference between functional outcome and pain reduction in both groups, post op rehabilitation vs pre & post rehabilitation
Mat Eillsmail et al.	n=26, male=5, female=21, age=64.3	n=24, male=2, female=22, age=62.4	Stationary bike Low resistance cycling, Isometric quadriceps, Inner range quadriceps, Hamstring stretch, Straight leg raise Leg raised to 45°	Not significant in the sports and recreational activities for both groups. No significant difference in ROM, no significant impact on short-term functional outcomes (KOOS subscales), and ROM of the knee following primary TKA.
Jahic et al.	n=10, males=3, females=7 BMI=25-30, Age =48-70YO, male:59.0 ± 9.47, female :59.7 ± 6.28	n=10, males=3, females=7, BMI=25-30, Age =48-70YO, male:59.0 ± 9.47, female :59.7 ± 6.28	Isometric & isotonic exercise with quadriceps strengthening flexibility and resistance training.	Prehabilitation group shows significant difference regarding the Knee Score

Federico Pozzi et al.	N= 88, female=50, male = 38, age 50-82 YO, Height= 147-190 cm, weight= 76.44(15.6), BMI=26.42(4.21)	A) progressive strengthening group (PST); N= 165, female=72, male = 93, age 48-84 YO, Height= 147-193 cm, weight= 90.04(116.4), BMI=30.69(4.28),	The progressive strengthening rehabilitation, range of motion (ROM) exercises, stationary cycling, and various straight leg raising exercises with weights	the control group had higher KOS-ADL score, greater active knee ROM, greater strength, and better performance compared to intervention group
Skoffler et al.	N= 25, Female= 17, Male= 12, Age= 70.1(6.4), BMI=31.8(24.3-42.2).	N= 29, Female= 19, Male= 11, Age= 70.7 (7.3), BMI= 30 (22.6-42.5)	Progressive resistance training (PRT) program (leg press, knee extension, knee flexion)	No significant differences between groups in the 30-second Chair Stand Test or for other functional performance tests, significantly larger improvements in normalized isometric knee extensor and knee flexor muscle strength of the operated leg in the intervention group. No differences in ROM both groups
Iskender et al.	N=30, Female= 26, Male= 4, Age 48-80, BMI= 25-43,	N= 30, Female= 26, Male= 4, Age= 50-81, BMI= 24-47,	mobilization and exercise trainings	State Anxiety scores & patient mobility scale in intev. Group is significantly lower than the control group,
Cavill et al.	N= 20, Female =11, Male= 9, Age 68.3(9.1)	N= 21, Female=11, Male= 10, Age= 66(8.4)	Static quad contractions, Straight leg raise, Knee extension stretch with a towel under the heel	

Pua et al	N=76, female=46, male =29, Isotonic exercise, Age= 64 (7), weight= 67(13)	N= 76, female= 46, male=29, Isotonic exercise in 40- & 70-degree flexion, Age= 64 (7), weight= 67(13)	Isotonic and Isometric in 40- & 70-degree flexion and evaluation of gait speed, quadriceps strength	No difference between power but Isometric reduce pain more than Isotonic exercise
Labraca et al.	N= 153,	N= 153	Static and isometric exercises, static quadriceps exercise, dynamic quadriceps exercise between 0 and 30 degrees of flexion, straight leg raise, and passive or active-assisted flexion exercises	Earlier onset of treatment also reduced pain and improved the range of motion and muscle strength, Physical therapy in the first 24 hours post-op improves autonomy in daily life activities, balance, and gait, reduces hospital stay in comparison to therapy applied at 48–72 hours post-surgery.
Kondo et al.	N 31, female= 29, male= 2, Age = 75.5(6.1), BMI= 27.5(4.1)	N= 31, female= 28, male = 2, Age= 75.8(5.8) , BMI= 26.3 (3.5)	Isometric quadriceps muscle exercise	There was no difference in all outcome measures between the two groups before TKA but in the intervention group (1-3 weeks after TKA); significant decrease in VAS scores, significant improvement in 10-m gait speed, and TUG

Lin et al.	N= 100, male= 18, female= 82, Age= 69.2(7.3), BMI= 27.6(4.8)	N= 100, male= 22, female= 78, Age= 68.3(8.7), BMI= 27.6(4.8)	squat with slightly bend their knees (15–30°) and then hold that position for approximately 10 min	KOOS subscales (pain, symptoms, ADL, Sport & activity, QOL) in intervention group was significantly greater than control group
Aytekin et al.	N= 23, Female=18, Male= 5, Age= 69.7(6.4), BMI= 30.2 (4.9)	N=21, Female= 18, Male= 3, Age= 67.8(6.3), BMI= 32.8 (5.9)	home-based exercise program (ankle pumping, knee range of motion, straight leg rising, quadriceps isometric, stretching and strengthening)	No significant differences in VAS score at rest (pr), VAS at activity (pa) & all subscales of KOOS at third and sixth month.
Tanaka.et al	Analyzed n=21, Age 76.7 (+/- 6.5) Gender; female=18, Male=3, Weight=62.0 (+/- 10.9)	Analyzed n=21, Age=77.3 (+/-6.8), Gender; female=14, male=7, Weight=60.0 (+/- 14.8)	Isometric and isotonic exercise such as squatting straight leg raising, climbing	No significant intergroup differences in either score not significantly improve ADL

Calatayud et al.	n=22, age=66.7, Weight=80.9, Height=1.6, BMI=31	n=22, age=66.8, Weight=82.1, Height=1.6, BMI=32	Increase lower limb muscle strength. with isometric & isotonic exercises	Isometric knee flexion, isometric hip abduction, VAS, WOMAC, ROM, and all the functional assessments were greater for the intervention group compared with the control. Pain decreases, improve lower limb muscle strength, ROM, and functional task performance before surgery, resulting in a reduced LOS at the hospital and faster physical and functional recovery after TKA.
Granicher et al.	n=10, male=5, female=5, age=68.1, weight=80.3, height=168.35, Deviation of the knee joint axis=12.4	n=10, male=7, female=3, age=66.6, weight=90.2, height=174.2, deviation of the knee joint axis=9.0	Training consisted of training on a bicycle ergometer, pedal trainer, treadmill, or cross trainer with light to moderate exercise intensity without pain provocation; quadriceps and hamstring muscles training, patient education for isometric & isometric exercises	Prehabilitation improves levels of physical activity, shorter recovery period after TKA

Villadsen A. et al	KNEE; n=40, female=24, age=65.1, BMI=33.4, KOOS/HOOS: ADL=43.9, Pain=39.7, Symptoms=49.3, Sports and Recreation=10.7, Quality of Life=27.1; EQ5D index= 0.60, EQ5D VAS=57.3	KNEE; n=41, female=25, age=67.1, BMI=30.8, KOOS/HOOS: ADL=53.3, Pain=47.8, Symptoms=57.8, Sports and Recreation=20.0, Quality of Life=30.9; EQ5D index= 0.66, EQ5D VAS=62.9	isotonic & isometric exercise training	no statistically significant difference in effects for ADL, the intervention group experienced a statistically significant short-term benefit in ADL and pain
Clode et al.	N= 23, Male= 12, Female= 11, Age 62.48) 12.61)	N= 52, Male = 26, Female= 26, Age 67.63(8.66)	isotonic & isometric exercise & quadriceps strengthening exercises	statistically significant improvements in pain and function prior to surgery especially in TUG, 5xSTS, but small improvement in self-reported function, pain and quality of life.
McKay et al	n=12, female=8, age=60.58, BMI=33.78	n=10, female=5, age=63.5, BMI=35.03	Treadmill, cycling ergometer, rowing ergometer, or recumbent stepper, followed by a circuit of bilateral lower body exercises (standing calf raise, seated leg press, leg curl, knee extension). Calf raises with bodyweight only	Analysis of the results suggests that quadriceps strength may not drive functional improvements after surgery.
Brown et al.	n=15 BMI= 34.6, four patients lost at 5 mo. follow-up, n at 3 mo.= 7	n=17 BMI=38.8, four patients lost at 5 mo. follow-up, n at 3 mo.= 11	The intervention consisted of rehabilitative, resistance stretching step exercises	higher mean QOL in the intervention group

Author	Characteristics/ Control group	Characteristics/ Intrv. group	Intervention	Outcome
Swank et.al	N:35, Age: 62.6(7.6), Weight: 95.3(23.4), BMI: 32.9(5.7), Race: white 30, Minority 4, Gender: male 13, female 22	N:36, Age: 63.1(7.3), Weight: 98.9(19.9), BMI: 35.9(8.5), Race: white 28, Minority 7, Gender: male 12, female 24	usual care (UC)group (n= 36) or usual care and exercise (UC + EX) group (n=35); included resistance training using bands, flexibility, and step training at least 3 times per week for 4–8 weeks before their TKA in addition to UC	functional outcome improved by prehabilitation, but it does not improve pain
Alghadir et al.	N=25, female=9, male 16, Age= 48-80, post-op rehabilitation	N=25, female=9, male 16, Age= 48-80, pre & post op rehabilitation	Strengthening and mobility exercises, proper techniques of transfers, and gait training with assistive devices (stick or walker)	no difference between functional outcome and pain reduction in both groups, post op rehabilitation vs pre & post rehabilitation
Mat Eillsmail et al.	n=26, male=5, female=21, age=64.3	n=24, male=2, female=22, age=62.4	Stationary bike Low resistance cycling, Isometric quadriceps, Inner range quadriceps, Hamstring stretch, Straight leg raise Leg raised to 45°	Not significant in the sports and recreational activities for both groups. No significant difference in ROM, no significant impact on short-term functional outcomes (KOOS subscales), and ROM of the knee following primary TKA.
Jahic et al.	n=10, males=3, females=7 BMI=25-30, Age =48-70YO, male:59.0 ± 9.47, female :59.7 ± 6.28	n=10, males=3, females=7, BMI=25-30, Age =48-70YO, male:59.0 ± 9.47, female :59.7 ± 6.28	Isometric & isotonic exercise with quadriceps strengthening flexibility and resistance training.	Prehabilitation group shows significant difference regarding the Knee Score

Federico Pozzi et al.	N= 88, female=50, male = 38, age 50-82 YO, Height= 147-190 cm, weight= 76.44(15.6), BMI=26.42(4.21)	A) progressive strengthening group (PST); N= 165, female=72, male = 93, age 48-84 YO, Height= 147-193 cm, weight= 90.04(116.4), BMI=30.69(4.28),	The progressive strengthening rehabilitation, range of motion (ROM) exercises, stationary cycling, and various straight leg raising exercises with weights	the control group had higher KOS-ADL score, greater active knee ROM, greater strength, and better performance compared to intervention group
Skoffler et al.	N= 25, Female= 17, Male= 12, Age= 70.1(6.4), BMI=31.8(24.3-42.2).	N= 29, Female= 19, Male= 11, Age= 70.7 (7.3), BMI= 30 (22.6-42.5)	Progressive resistance training (PRT) program (leg press, knee extension, knee flexion)	No significant differences between groups in the 30-second Chair Stand Test or for other functional performance tests, significantly larger improvements in normalized isometric knee extensor and knee flexor muscle strength of the operated leg in the intervention group. No differences in ROM both groups
Iskender et al.	N=30, Female= 26, Male= 4, Age 48-80, BMI= 25-43,	N= 30, Female= 26, Male= 4, Age= 50-81, BMI= 24-47,	mobilization and exercise trainings	State Anxiety scores & patient mobility scale in Intev. Group is significantly lower than the control group,
Cavill et al.	N= 20, Female =11, Male= 9, Age 68.3(9.1)	N= 21, Female=11, Male= 10, Age= 66(8.4)	Static quad contractions, Straight leg raise, Knee extension stretch with a towel under the heel	

Pua et al	N=76, female=46, male =29, Isotonic exercise, Age= 64 (7), weight= 67(13)	N= 76, female= 46, male=29, Isotonic exercise in 40- & 70-degree flexion, Age= 64 (7), weight= 67(13)	Isotonic and Isometric in 40- & 70-degree flexion and evaluation of gait speed, quadriceps strength	No difference between power but Isometric reduce pain more than Isotonic exercise
Labraca et al.	N= 153,	N= 153	Static and isometric exercises, static quadriceps exercise, dynamic quadriceps exercise between 0 and 30 degrees of flexion, straight leg raise, and passive or active-assisted flexion exercises	Earlier onset of treatment also reduced pain and improved the range of motion and muscle strength, Physical therapy in the first 24 hours post-op improves autonomy in daily life activities, balance, and gait, reduces hospital stay in comparison to therapy applied at 48–72 hours post-surgery.
Kondo et al.	N 31, female= 29, male= 2, Age = 75.5(6.1), BMI= 27.5(4.1)	N= 31, female= 28, male = 2, Age= 75.8(5.8), BMI= 26.3 (3.5)	Isometric quadriceps muscle exercise	There was no difference in all outcome measures between the two groups before TKA but in the intervention group (1-3 weeks after TKA); significant decrease in VAS scores, significant improvement in 10-m gait speed, and TUG

Lin et al.	N= 100, male= 18, female= 82, Age= 69.2(7.3), BMI= 27.6(4.8)	N= 100, male= 22, female= 78, Age= 68.3(8.7), BMI= 27.6(4.8)	squat with slightly bend their knees (15–30°) and then hold that position for approximately 10 min	KOOS subscales (pain, symptoms, ADL, Sport & activity, QOL) in intervention group was significantly greater than control group
Aytekin et al.	N= 23, Female=18, Male= 5, Age= 69.7(6.4), BMI= 30.2 (4.9)	N=21, Female= 18, Male= 3, Age= 67.8(6.3), BMI= 32.8 (5.9)	home-based exercise program (ankle pumping, knee range of motion, straight leg rising, quadriceps isometric, stretching and strengthening)	No significant differences in VAS score at rest (pr), VAS at activity (pa) & all subscales of KOOS at third and sixth month.
Tanaka.et al	Analyzed n=21, Age 76.7 (+/- 6.5) Gender; female=18, Male=3, Weight=62.0 (+/- 10.9)	Analyzed n=21, Age=77.3 (+/-6.8), Gender; female=14, male=7, Weight=60.0 (+/- 14.8)	Isometric and isotonic exercise such as squatting straight leg raising, climbing	No significant intergroup differences in either score not significantly improve ADL

Calatayud et al.	n=22, age=66.7, Weight=80.9, Height=1.6, BMI=31	n=22, age=66.8, Weight=82.1, Height=1.6, BMI=32	Increase lower limb muscle strength. with isometric & isotonic exercises	Isometric knee flexion, isometric hip abduction, VAS, WOMAC, ROM, and all the functional assessments were greater for the intervention group compared with the control. Pain decreases, improve lower limb muscle strength, ROM, and functional task performance before surgery, resulting in a reduced LOS at the hospital and faster physical and functional recovery after TKA.
Granicher et al.	n=10, male=5, female=5, age=68.1, weight=80.3, height=168.35, Deviation of the knee joint axis=12.4	n=10, male=7, female=3, age=66.6, weight=90.2, height=174.2, deviation of the knee joint axis=9.0	Training consisted of training on a bicycle ergometer, pedal trainer, treadmill, or cross trainer with light to moderate exercise intensity without pain provocation; quadriceps and hamstring muscles training, patient education for isometric & isometric exercises	Prehabilitation improves levels of physical activity, shorter recovery period after TKA

Villadsen A. et al	KNEE; n=40, female=24, age=65.1, BMI=33.4, KOOS/HOOS: ADL=43.9, Pain=39.7, Symptoms=49.3, Sports and Recreation=10.7, Quality of Life=27.1; EQ5D index= 0.60, EQ5D VAS=57.3	KNEE; n=41, female=25, age=67.1, BMI=30.8, KOOS/HOOS: ADL=53.3, Pain=47.8, Symptoms=57.8, Sports and Recreation=20.0, Quality of Life=30.9; EQ5D index= 0.66, EQ5D VAS=62.9	isotonic & isometric exercise training	no statistically significant difference in effects for ADL, the intervention group experienced a statistically significant short-term benefit in ADL and pain
Clode et al.	N= 23, Male= 12, Female= 11, Age 62.48) 12.61)	N= 52, Male = 26, Female= 26, Age 67.63(8.66)	isotonic & isometric exercise & quadriceps strengthening exercises	statistically significant improvements in pain and function prior to surgery especially in TUG, 5xSTS, but small improvement in self-reported function, pain and quality of life.
McKay et al	n=12, female=8, age=60.58, BMI=33.78	n=10, female=5, age=63.5, BMI=35.03	Treadmill, cycling ergometer, rowing ergometer, or recumbent stepper, followed by a circuit of bilateral lower body exercises (standing calf raise, seated leg press, leg curl, knee extension). Calf raises with bodyweight only	Analysis of the results suggests that quadriceps strength may not drive functional improvements after surgery.
Brown et al.	n=15 BMI= 34.6, four patients lost at 5 mo. follow-up, n at 3 mo.= 7	n=17 BMI=38.8, four patients lost at 5 mo. follow-up, n at 3 mo.= 11	The intervention consisted of rehabilitative, resistance stretching step exercises	higher mean QOL in the intervention group

Table 3: Tabulated data outcome measurement, baseline & final data [7], [22]–[48]²⁷⁻⁶⁰

Fig. 2: VAS score; pre-op Rehab group vs. Control Group

Fig. 3: TUG; Pre-op Rehab Group vs. Control Group

Fig. 5: ROM; Pre-op Rehab Group vs. Control Group

Fig. 6: 6MW; Pre-op Rehab Group vs. Control Group

Fig. 7: ADL: Pre-op Rehab Group vs. Control Group

Fig. 9: TUG; Post-op Rehab Group vs. Control Group

Fig. 10: 6MW; Post-op Rehab Group vs. Control Group

Fig. 11: ADL; Post-op Rehab Group vs. Control Group

Fig. 12: QOL; Post-op Rehab Group vs. Control Group

Fig. 13: Sport & Activities; Post-op Rehab vs. Control Group

Prehabilitation compared to Usual Care for Patient with TKA

Bibliography:

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of the evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With Usual Care	With Prehabilitation		The risk with Usual Care	Risk difference with Prehabilitation

VAS Score

942 (5 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕⊕ High	224/471 (47.6%)	247/471 (52.4%)	not estimable	476 per 1,000	
-----------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	------	------------------	--------------------	--------------------	---------------	---------------	--

TUG

396 (4 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕⊕ High	85/198 (42.9%)	113/198 (57.1%)	not estimable	429 per 1,000	
-----------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	------	------------------	-------------------	--------------------	---------------	---------------	--

ROM

136 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕⊕ High	33/68 (48.5%)	35/68 (51.5%)	not estimable	485 per 1,000	
-----------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	------	------------------	------------------	------------------	---------------	---------------	--

6MWT

250 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕○ Moderate	60/125 (48.0%)	65/125 (52.0%)	not estimable	480 per 1,000	
-----------------	-------------	-------------	---------	-------------	------	----------------------	-------------------	-------------------	---------------	---------------	--

ADL

Prehabilitation compared to Usual Care for Patient with TKA

Bibliography:

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
228 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕○ Moderate	51/14 (44.7%)	53/114 (46.5%)	not estimable	447 per 1,000	

Table 4: GRADEpro GDT results for outcomes in Prehabilitation group

Post-operative Rehabilitation compared to Usual care for Patient with TKA

Bibliography:

Certainty assessment							Summary of findings				
Participants (studies) Follow-up	Risk of bias	Inconsistency	Indirectness	Imprecision	Publication bias	Overall certainty of the evidence	Study event rates (%)		Relative effect (95% CI)	Anticipated absolute effects	
							With Usual care	With Post-operative Rehabilitation		The risk with Usual care	Risk difference with Post-operative Rehabilitation
686 (3 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕⊕ High	171/343 (49.9%)	172/343 (50.1%)	not estimable	499 per 1,000	

TUG

686 (3 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕⊕ High	171/343 (49.9%)	172/343 (50.1%)	not estimable	499 per 1,000	
-----------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	-------------	------	------------------	--------------------	--------------------	---------------	---------------------	--

6MWT

630 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕○ Moderate	119/315 (37.8%)	196/315 (62.2%)	not estimable	378 per 1,000	
-----------------	-------------	-------------	---------	-------------	------	----------------------	--------------------	--------------------	---------------	---------------------	--

Post-operative Rehabilitation compared to Usual care for Patient with TKA

Bibliography:

Certainty assessment						Summary of findings					
ADL											
930 (3 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕⊕ High	159/465 (34.2%)	306/465 (65.8%)	not estimable	342 per 1,000	
QOL											
424 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	not serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕⊕ High	71/12 (33.5%)	141/212 (66.5%)	not estimable	335 per 1,000	
sport & activities											
424 (2 RCTs)	not serious	not serious	not serious	serious	none	⊕⊕ ⊕○ Moderate	71/12 (33.5%)	141/212 (66.5%)	not estimable	335 per 1,000	

Table 5: GRADEpro GDT results for outcomes in post-operative group